

Three Years of TIJFS: Observations, Current Practices and Future Perspective

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The International Journal of Frontier Sciences just completed its three years of publication. Start of a journal is always challenging for editors especially if journal is not an official publication of some institute or professional society. However, completing three years also has been a very learning experience for editorial team.

From the start, TIJFS team is focused to catch indexation in EMBASE, MEDLINE, PubMed, Scopus and Web of Science. However, starting years of the journal are always challenging. Journal editors are continuously improving practices to achieve these milestones at earliest. In scope, journal is transdisciplinary mainly covering life and environmental sciences. Starting from Pakistan, it was very difficult to run an internationally covered journal, however, our international editorial team putting its continuous efforts to do this. In last year, journal started its indexing process and just became a part of WHO's Index Medicus. Also, editors started to generate digital object identifiers (DOIs) of all manuscripts published. Currently, journal is in process of indexation in prestigious international bodies including Web of Science etc. Journal editors hope to be a part of many international indices during the current volume year. Also, its worth to mention that journal is following ethical guidelines by Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials, Committee of Publication Ethics, International Committee of Medical Journal Editors and World Association of Medical Editors.

Current volume contains original articles, clinical audit and a report covering broad spectrum domains of life sciences especially medical science including topics of clinical chemistry, dentistry, gynaecology, neurosurgery, nutrition, pain medicine, public health, rehabilitation, sleep medicine, surgery and virology.